

Sustainable strengthening of CoCrFeNiMn high-entropy alloy using NbC–Nb(C) composite synthesized from recycled carbon precursors

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ABSTRACT

This study presents a sustainable approach to the synthesis of niobium carbide (NbC) using carbon obtained from thermal plasma valorisation of waste polypropylene (PP), followed by its application as a ceramic reinforcement in CoCrFeNiMn high-entropy alloy (HEA) produced via powder metallurgy. Pure niobium powder and carbon soot were mechanically alloyed as raw materials in Nb: C ratios of 1:1 and 1:2 under high-energy ball milling for up to 8 h, both with and without n-heptane as a process control agent (PCA). Phase formation was monitored using X-ray diffraction (XRD), while scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and energy-dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) were employed to characterize the particle morphology and composition. The absence of n-heptane favoured NbC formation and prevented pyrophoric oxidation, with a Nb: C ratio of 1:1, yielding approximately 19 wt% NbC after only 4 h of milling, while the remaining fraction consisted predominantly of carbon-supersaturated Nb(C), serving as a highly reactive precursor for subsequent NbC formation. The 4 h NbC powders were subsequently incorporated into CoCrFeNiMn HEA at 5, 10, and 15 wt% and consolidated by spark plasma sintering (SPS) at 1000 °C under a pressure of 48 MPa. Mechanical testing revealed an increase in compressive yield strength (CYS) with increasing NbC content, starting already at 5 wt% NbC and reaching an approximately 40% improvement at 15 wt% NbC compared to the unreinforced alloy. At the highest investigated loading, the composite achieved a yield strength of 717 MPa and a hardness of 310 HV30, corresponding to a nearly 15% increase in hardness, while retaining excellent compressive plasticity (>40%).

1. Introduction

The growing global demand for high-performance materials in energy, aerospace, and transportation sectors has intensified the search for alloys that combine exceptional mechanical strength, thermal stability, and corrosion resistance while also addressing modern sustainability requirements [1–4]. Among the emerging candidates, high-entropy alloys (HEAs) have gained significant attention due to their unique compositional design and outstanding mechanical and functional

properties [5–7]. Unlike conventional alloys, which are typically built around one or two principal elements, HEAs consist of five or more elements in near-equiatomic ratios, resulting in high configurational entropy that stabilizes simple solid-solution phases, such as face-centred cubic (FCC) or body-centred cubic (BCC) structures [5,8,9]. These alloys commonly exhibit superior strength, hardness, wear resistance, and thermal stability compared to traditional alloys, making them promising for advanced engineering applications [10,11].

Among various HEAs, the CoCrFeNiMn alloy, commonly referred to

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as the Cantor alloy, is one of the most studied due to its excellent ductility, corrosion resistance, and fracture toughness [5,8,12–14]. However, its limited hardness and only quite low yield strength at room temperature constrain its application in environments requiring high wear resistance or load-bearing performance [15–17]. To overcome these limitations, ceramic particle reinforcement has been widely explored as an effective strategy for strengthening HEAs through mechanisms such as load transfer, grain refinement, and thermal mismatch [17,18]. In this context, niobium carbide (NbC) emerges as a particularly attractive reinforcement due to its high melting point, hardness, and chemical stability, as well as its excellent compatibility with metallic matrices [19–22].

Traditionally, NbC synthesis relies on high-temperature carbothermal reduction processes using pure graphite, a route that is both energy-intensive and environmentally irresponsible [23]. In contrast, mechanical alloying (MA) offers a cleaner and more efficient alternative, enabling solid-state reactions between metal and carbon powders at lower temperatures [24–28]. Moreover, utilizing carbon derived from polymer waste or other recycled sources as a precursor aligns with the growing emphasis on sustainable materials engineering, offering both cost-effective and eco-friendly routes to advanced carbide synthesis [29–40].

In this study, niobium carbide (NbC) powders were synthesized by mechanical alloying using carbon obtained from polypropylene plasma thermochemical treatment by-products, providing a sustainable waste-derived carbon source. Similar plasma-based and thermochemical valorisation routes for plastic-to-carbon (or waste-to-carbon in general) conversion are well-documented and demonstrate the feasibility of obtaining reactive carbon suitable for advanced materials synthesis [34, 41–49]. The effects of milling time, Nb: C ratio, and the use of n-heptane as a process control agent were systematically examined to describe the NbC phase evolution. This approach is consistent with other studies, which have shown that MA parameters critically influence carbide formation, grain size, and micro strain [50–53]. The resulting carbides were subsequently used to reinforce CoCrFeNiMn high-entropy alloys produced via powder metallurgy and consolidated by spark plasma sintering (SPS), a method widely applied for HEA-ceramic composites

due to its fast heating and ability to retain fine microstructure [54,55].

The mechanical and microstructural properties of the composites were characterized to evaluate the strengthening effect of NbC reinforcement, following the well-established understanding that finite, well-dispersed carbide or ceramic fractions significantly enhance hardness, yield strength, wear resistance, and high-temperature stability in HEA matrices [17,19–22,56–58]. This work contributes to the development of eco-efficient high-entropy alloy composites, demonstrating how recycled carbon materials can be transformed into functional reinforcements that enhance performance while supporting sustainability frameworks such as green chemistry, circular economy, and low-carbon metallurgy, which are, for instance, also addressed in Refs. [30,32,34, 35,37,38,59,60]. The findings offer insights into the correlation between synthesis parameters, microstructural evolution, and mechanical behavior, thereby enabling the sustainable design of next-generation structural materials.

2. Methodology

The overall process is illustrated in Fig. 1. Individual steps, including polypropylene (PP) thermochemical plasma process, synthesis of niobium carbide via MA method, and preparation of reinforced CoCrFeNiMn via NbC, are described in detail in the following subchapters.

2.1. Pure carbon harvesting from the PP thermochemical plasma process

Carbon used for NbC synthesis was obtained through thermochemical recycling of PP plastic waste using a 100 kW microwave plasma system, the PlasGas reactor, designed for plasma-chemical valorisation processes. A comprehensive thermochemical plasma process for PP gasification was investigated in our previous study and publication, including carbon yield, energy balance, and gas analysis [61]. The schematic of the setup and the image are shown in Fig. 2.

The PlasGas reactor has been previously employed for processing natural gas, mixed wastes, and plastics using a water-stabilized arc plasma torch [62–64]. Similar plasma-assisted waste valorisation routes have been studied, for instance, in Refs. [41–45,47,49]. In this process,

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of the entire process, including thermochemical Plasma processing for PP plastic, MA process for NbC synthesis, and SPS method for reinforcing CoCrFeNiMn via NbC.

Fig. 2. a)Schematic of the experiment setup includes a Microwave Plasma torch system, Reactor, Hopper, Quenching tower, and solid carbon Filtration system for PP plasma thermochemical treatment and carbon production. b) Image of microwave plasma torch installed on a plasma chemical reactor, PlasGas [61].

PP granules were fed into a high-temperature plasma zone inside the reactor operating at $\sim 1200\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ under an air atmosphere. The plasma facilitated the complete decomposition of the PP into hydrogen-rich syngas and solid carbon nanomaterials.

Microwave plasma PP thermochemical processing has been performed under different operating conditions, including different Plasma power and different PP granule feeding rates. The solid carbon used in this work was selected from the operating conditions with 40 kW of

Microwave plasma power and a PP feeding rate of 18 kg/h. The solid carbon, formed as a by-product of incomplete gasification and pyrolysis, was entrained in the syngas stream and subsequently separated and collected using a multi-stage filtration system after cooling. Consistent with prior observations, pyrolysis, gasification, and plasma conversion of polymer waste can yield reactive carbon chars or nanocarbons suitable for material applications [31,36,39,40,65–70]. Detailed preparation steps for the recovery of solid carbon from the filtering system of the PlasGas reactor facility are explained in Ref. [61]. The recovered carbon was characterized using high-resolution transmission electron microscope (HRTEM), transmission electron microscope coupled with energy dispersive spectroscopy (TEM/EDS), Brunauer-Emmett-Teller analysis (BET), laser diffraction (LD), and Raman Spectroscopy. The approach can be related to concepts found in waste-to-carbon research, where plastic-derived chars are discussed as possible precursors for activated carbon, nanocarbons, and carbide synthesis [29,67,69].

2.2. Synthesis of Niobium Carbide (NbC)

Niobium carbide (NbC) powders were synthesized via mechanical alloying (MA) using pure niobium (Nb) and carbon derived from polypropylene (PP) pyrolysis by-products as raw materials. Mechanical alloying is widely recognized for enabling the formation of carbides and nanostructured composites at reduced temperatures via repeated cold welding and fracturing [24–28]. Prior studies have shown that milling parameters, carbon reactivity, the use of PCA, and powder stoichiometry strongly influence carbide formation, morphology, and crystallite size [23,50–53,71]. The carbon precursor, obtained from the plasma-assisted pyrolysis of waste PP, was first ground to a fine powder and sieved to $<63\ \mu\text{m}$. The Nb and C powders were weighed in two different stoichiometric ratios, 1:1 and 1:2, to examine the influence of carbon content on carbide formation.

The powder mixtures (batches of 20 g) were processed in a Retsch PM 100 planetary ball mill, using a stainless-steel jar and ten steel balls, corresponding to a ball-to-powder weight ratio (BPR) of 15:1. Milling was performed at 400 rpm under an argon atmosphere with a controlled argon flow of 2 slm to prevent oxidation. Some batches were processed with 4 wt% n-heptane added as a PCA, while others were prepared without PCA to evaluate its effect on carbide phase evolution and powder reactivity.

Each milling cycle consisted of 30 min of alloying followed by a 10-min pause to prevent excessive temperature rise in the milling vessel. Samples were collected after 2, 4, 6, and 8 h of milling to monitor phase evolution. The resulting powders were characterized by X-ray diffraction (XRD) to identify the phase composition and crystallite size evolution, while SEM/EDS was used to examine the morphology and elemental distribution.

2.3. Preparation of reinforced CoCrFeNiMn via NbC

The CoCrFeNiMn high-entropy alloy (HEA) matrix was prepared using commercial gas-atomized alloy powder with particle sizes ranging from 15 to 53 μm . The selected NbC powder, obtained after 4 h of mechanical alloying, was incorporated into the HEA matrix in three different proportions (5 wt%, 10 wt%, and 15 wt%) to evaluate the strengthening efficiency, consistent with typical reinforcing ranges used in HEA-ceramic composite systems [17,54].

Each composite powder mixture was homogenized using a planetary ball mill under an argon atmosphere, employing the same parameters as those used in the NbC synthesis step (20 g of powder, 15:1 ball-to-powder ratio, 400 rpm, 30 min milling). 4 wt% n-heptane was used as a PCA to enhance dispersion, reduce cold welding, and prevent particle agglomeration.

Following homogenization, the composite powders were consolidated using spark plasma sintering (SPS) on an FCT HP D 10 system. The sintering process was carried out under vacuum conditions at a heating

rate of $200\ ^\circ\text{C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ up to $1000\ ^\circ\text{C}$, with an applied uniaxial pressure of 48 MPa and a holding time of 10 min, and compressed with a force of 15 kN. The samples were then cooled to room temperature inside the SPS chamber to prevent surface oxidation and thermal shock. For each sample, 10 g of the synthesized powder was consolidated into a cylindrical compact with a diameter of 20 mm and a nominal height of approximately 4 mm. The SPS parameters were selected based on our previous publications [13,14,72–76] focused on a variety of high-entropy alloys with Cantor or Cantor-derived compositions, in order to ensure maximum densification while preventing excessive grain coarsening.

The resulting compacts were cross-sectioned and prepared for metallographic observation. Microstructural characterization was conducted using optical microscopy, SEM/EDS, and XRD to evaluate the distribution of NbC particles and the integrity of the matrix. Vickers hardness testing (HV30) and uniaxial compression tests were conducted to assess mechanical performance. For these tests, cuboidal samples with a square base were used, with the height corresponding to 1.5 times the side length of the square base, while the strain rate was set to $0.001\ \text{s}^{-1}$.

2.4. Characterization

Understanding the structural and compositional properties of materials is crucial in materials science. In this work, a combination of structural, microstructural, and mechanical characterization techniques was employed to evaluate phase formation, morphology, elemental distribution, and bulk properties of both the NbC powders and the NbC-reinforced HEA composites.

Raman spectroscopy was performed using an inVia Raman microscope (Renishaw, England) equipped with a CCD detector in backscattering geometry. A DPSS laser (532 nm, 50 mW) with a $50\times$ magnification objective was used for spectral acquisition. Measurement was performed with a 1.25 mW laser power and 20 times data accumulation. The instrument was calibrated with a silicon reference ($520\ \text{cm}^{-1}$) and a resolution of $<1\ \text{cm}^{-1}$.

High-resolution transmission electron microscopy (HR-TEM) was performed using an EFTEM (energy-filtering transmission electron microscopy) Jeol 2200FS EFTEM (200 kV) instrument equipped with an EDS detector (Oxford Instruments). An acceleration voltage of up to 200 keV was used for imaging. Sample preparation was performed by drop-casting the suspension ($1\ \text{mg}\ \text{mL}^{-1}$ in ethanol) on a TEM grid (Cu; 400 mesh; carbon film) followed by drying at $30\ ^\circ\text{C}$ for 2 h.

Simultaneous thermal analysis (STA) was performed using the Setaram Setsys Evolution apparatus with a temperature range of up to $1300\ ^\circ\text{C}$. The measurements were performed in a dynamic helium atmosphere with a flow rate of $50\ \text{mL}\ \text{min}^{-1}$ and a heating rate of $10\ ^\circ\text{C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$. The mass spectrometer OmniStarTM from Pfeiffer Vacuum (Pfeiffer Vacuum GmbH, Aßlar, Germany) was used to analyse gases evolved during the heating.

X-ray powder diffraction (XRD) data were collected at room temperature on a Bruker D8 Discoverer powder diffractometer with parafocusing Bragg–Brentano geometry using $\text{Cu}\ \text{K}\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 0.15418\ \text{nm}$, $U = 40\ \text{kV}$, $I = 40\ \text{mA}$). Data were scanned over an angular range $5\text{--}90^\circ$ (2θ) with a step size of 0.019° (2θ). Data evaluation was performed using the EVA software package.

BET specific surface area was measured using a NOVA touch LX2 sorption analyser (Quantachrome Instruments). The sample was out-gassed for 10 h at $100\ ^\circ\text{C}$ under high vacuum. A nitrogen-cooled (77 K) detector was used to evaluate the results using the BET and Kelvin equations. The density functional theory (DFT) method is used for calculating pore volume and pore size distribution.

SEM-EDS-EBSD Analysis for the morphology was investigated using a Tescan Lyra dual-beam SEM equipped with an FEG electron source. Elemental composition and mapping were performed using an EDS analyzer (Oxford Instruments X-MaxN, $20\ \text{mm}^2$ SDD) with AZtecEnergy software. Metallographic cross-sections of the samples were ground and

polished using a polycrystalline diamond suspension before being etched in diluted aqua regia (HNO_3 and HCl in a 1:3 ratio, further diluted with distilled H_2O in a 1:1 ratio). Samples were then mounted on carbon-conductive tape.

For EBSD analysis, compact samples were additionally prepared by final ion polishing in order to minimize deformation, relief, carbide pull-out, and etching-related artefacts introduced during conventional metallographic preparation. Final surface polishing was carried out using a Gatan PECS 682 ion polishing system. The specimens were treated at an accelerating voltage of 10 keV for 5 min while rotating at 30 rpm. During polishing, the ion beam incidence angle was continuously oscillated between 0° and 85° , where 0° corresponds to normal incidence and 85° to a near-grazing angle. The angle was oscillated back and forth at a rate of 16° s^{-1} throughout the treatment.

EBSD analysis was performed on the ion-polished surfaces using a Thermo Fisher Apreo 2 SEM equipped with an Oxford Symmetry S3 EBSD camera. Where required, simultaneous or complementary EDS mapping was performed using an Ultim Max Infinity EDS detector. EBSD/EDS data were acquired at an accelerating voltage of 20 kV, a beam current of 13 nA, and a working distance of 20 mm. The EBSD patterns were stored and the zero-solution points in the orientation maps were reindexed using the MapSweeper routine in AZtecCrystal 3.3 software. For EBSD indexing of the CoCrFeNiMn matrix, a CIF file for fcc Co was modified by setting the lattice parameter to 3.598 Å and assigning equal Co, Cr, Fe, Mn, and Ni site occupancies of 0.2 to represent the equiatomic Cantor alloy composition.

For the unreinforced CoCrFeNiMn alloy, EBSD maps were acquired using step sizes of 0.03 μm and 0.3 μm to capture both local high-resolution and larger-area microstructural statistics. For the CoCrFeNiMn + NbC composite, EBSD/EDS analysis was focused on NbC-rich regions, including high-resolution maps used to determine the equivalent circle diameter (ECD) of fine NbC features and the distribution of low-angle and high-angle boundaries.

X-ray fluorescence (XRF) was used to determine the chemical composition using an Axios sequential WD-XRF spectrometer (PANalytical, Almelo, Netherlands) equipped with a Rh-anode end-window X-ray tube with a 50- μm Be window. Data were collected using SuperO software. The sample was pressed without binders onto an H_3BO_3 pellet to a total thickness of ~ 5 mm and a diameter of 40 mm.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Carbon characterization

Produced carbon from PP plastic thermochemical MW plasma recycling, initially characterized by electron microscopy for finding more insight regarding the micro and nano structure of carbon precursor for the MA process. TEM image revealed that the carbon nanoparticle size varies from a maximum of 300 nm to a minimum of ~ 20 nm. However, it appears that particles with a size larger than 50 nm have a nearly perfect spherical shape, whereas smaller particles are more semi-spherical but not in an exact shape. EDS mapping also confirms a spherical particle shape and shows that the material mainly contains the carbon element, with a trace concentration of oxygen. The map sum spectrum indicates that carbon concentration is ~ 99.5 at.%, and ~ 0.3 at.% is oxygen. The TEM image with EDS carbon and oxygen maps is shown in Fig. 3.

For the investigation of carbon material nanostructure, HRTEM has been conducted, and high-resolution images are shown in Fig. 4.

HRTEM revealed information about the structure of carbon particles below 50 nm, as shown in Fig. 4a, indicating that the particles appear to have more than one nucleation centre. During thermochemical plasma PP recycling, carbon particles nucleate and interconnect, forming multiple nucleation seeds for further particle growth. Additionally, Fig. 4b, at higher resolution, reveals that particles are not completely independent, and there are not only physical bonds but also chemical bonds that

Fig. 3. TEM image and EDS map for carbon and oxygen, and the map sum spectrum of the produced carbon used for the MA process.

Fig. 4. HRTEM images of carbon material with a)200K and b)300K magnification.

connect particles on the surface of each particle to other particles, thereby forming carbon aggregation from primary nanoparticles.

Texture analysis and specific surface area measurement have been performed using the BET method to elucidate the porosity structure of the carbon material. The specific surface area was $28.75 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$, as calculated by the BET method, which illustrates the carbon surface nitrogen gas adsorption and desorption at each P/P_0 , as shown in Fig. 5a. Also, nitrogen gas isotherm adsorption and desorption graph interpreted by DFT method for Pore volume and pore size distribution has been done, and results are shown in Fig. 5b, where the pore volume was $0.05 \text{ cm}^3/\text{g}$, and the maximum pore size is $\sim 5 \text{ nm}$, which means the carbon material is mainly mesoporous.

The XRD pattern (Fig. 6) shows two characteristic diffraction peaks corresponding to the (002) and (100) planes of graphitic carbon. The dominant (002) peak appears at 2θ about 25.44° , which corresponds to an interlayer spacing (d_{002}) of 0.351 nm . This value is slightly larger than that of well-ordered graphite ($\sim 0.335 \text{ nm}$), indicating a turbostratic structure with reduced stacking order and the presence of defects or functional groups between graphene layers. The (100) peak, located at around 42.94° , is associated with the in-plane ordering of sp^2 carbon atoms. The relatively low intensity and broad nature of this peak suggest limited lateral crystallinity and small domain sizes. The calculated crystallite domain size (CDD) of approximately 2.3 nm further confirms that the material consists of nanoscale graphitic domains. This small size

indicates a low degree of graphitization and suggests that the structure consists of short-range-ordered carbon layers rather than well-developed graphite crystals.

The Raman spectrum of the carbon material, recorded using a 520 nm excitation laser, is shown in Fig. 7 and exhibits the characteristic D band at approximately 1357 cm^{-1} and the G band at around 1590 cm^{-1} , confirming the carbonaceous nature of the sample. The prominent D band indicates the presence of structural defects, disorder, and edge sites associated with sp^2 carbon domains, while the intense G band is attributed to the in-plane vibration of sp^2 -bonded carbon atoms in graphitic structures.

The comparable intensities of the D and G bands suggest a partially disordered carbon framework with limited graphitic ordering. In the second-order region, the appearance of a broad 2D band around 2642 cm^{-1} , together with a D + G combination band near 2927 cm^{-1} , further supports the presence of turbostratic or nanocrystalline graphitic domains rather than well-ordered graphite. Overall, the Raman features indicate that the material consists of defect-rich sp^2 carbon with small graphitic domains, a characteristic typical of plasma-synthesized or nanostructured carbon materials.

Laser diffraction particle size analysis, as shown in Fig. 8, illustrates a narrow and unimodal particle size distribution, with the dominant fraction centred in the micrometer range.

The volume-based distribution exhibits a clear maximum around $1 \mu\text{m}$

Fig. 5. a) isotherm nitrogen gas adsorption and desorption by carbon material, b) pore volume and pore size distribution calculated by the DFT method.

Fig. 6. XRD pattern of carbon precursor for NbC formation.

Fig. 7. Raman Spectroscopy of carbon material with decomposition of the spectrum to D, G, 2D, and D + G bands.

2 μm , while the cumulative curve indicates a median particle diameter (D50) of $\sim 1.45 \mu\text{m}$. Only a minor contribution of submicron particles and a limited tail toward larger sizes are observed, suggesting relatively uniform particle formation with low agglomeration. Overall, the results indicate a well-controlled particle size distribution suitable for reproducible processing and consistent material performance.

3.2. Synthesis & Characterization of NbC powders

The formation of niobium carbide during mechanical alloying (MA) was strongly influenced by both the milling atmosphere and the Nb: C stoichiometry. Quantitative Rietveld XRD analysis reveals significant differences in carbide phase evolutions between PCA-assisted milling and dry milling, as shown in Table 1 and supported with the XRD spectra (Fig. 9). The use of n-heptane as a PCA profoundly altered the

phase evolution during MA. Samples milled with n-heptane exhibited strong pyrophoric behavior. After opening the milling vessel, the powder ignited spontaneously, resulting in the rapid oxidation of the very fine powder particles. Thus, the 1:1 mixture with PCA contained predominantly oxide phases such as Nb_8O_{21} and NbO_2 even after 8 h of milling, whereas NbC formation remained below 10 wt%. One can see that even 8 h of MA still retained a high amount of unreacted Nb due to its ability to suppress the usually unwanted cold-welding processes. This behavior is attributed to the adsorption, lubrication, and/or decomposition of n-heptane under elevated temperatures and pressures generated during ball-powder collisions. The organic fluid might undergo partial cracking, leading to the formation of hydrogen and reactive radicals that adsorb onto the fresh, highly active niobium fracture surfaces, which (a) inhibited carbon diffusion into the Nb lattice and (b) destabilized the powder surface and reactivity [52,53,71]. Furthermore,

Fig. 8. Laser Diffraction Particle size distribution, including Volume density and Cumulative.

Table 1

Quantitative phase evolution (in wt.%) determined by XRD for Nb–C powder mixtures milled for different durations, comparing the effect of stoichiometry (1:1 vs. 1:2) and process control agent (with vs. without n-heptane).

PCA (n-heptane)	Nb: C Ratio	Phase	Time of MA/wt.%				
			0 h	2 h	4 h	6 h	8 h
With	1:1	Nb	100	99	22	34	29
		NbC	–	1	2	3	9
		Nb _{8,4} O ₂₁	–	–	75	42	8
		NbO ₂	–	–	–	21	49
		NbO	–	–	1	<1	5
	1:2	Nb	100	99	32	39	40
		NbC	–	1	1	1	2
		Nb _{8,4} O ₂₁	–	–	67	59	55
		NbO ₂	–	–	–	<1	3
		NbO	traces	–	–	1	–
Without	1:1	Nb	100	95	81	19	5
		NbC	–	5	19	80	92
		Nb _{8,4} O ₂₁	–	–	–	–	–
		NbO ₂	–	–	–	–	–
		NbO	–	–	–	–	–
	1:2	Nb	100	97	90	50	11
		NbC	–	3	9	30	69
		Nb _{8,4} O ₂₁	–	–	–	17	–
		NbO ₂	–	–	–	–	20
		NbO	–	–	–	–	–

the presence of hydrogen also affects the overall yield of carbide formation through its reduction behavior.

It was observed that the wet milling, while effective for achieving high powder yields and fine particle sizes in other alloy systems, led to pyrophoric behavior in the NbC synthesis. The n-heptane effectively suppressed cold welding, resulting in the production of extremely fine, non-passivated metallic surfaces. Upon exposure to the atmosphere during jar opening, the rapid oxidation of these high-energy surfaces triggered auto-ignition, making this approach unsuitable for this specific NbC synthesis route. These findings are confirmed by the morphological evolution shown in Fig. 10.

In contrast, dry milling (without PCA) enabled efficient mechanochemical synthesis of NbC. Carbide formation occurred rapidly in the 1:1 stoichiometric mixture, where ~19 wt% NbC was already detected

after 4 h of milling, which is shown in Table 1. Continued milling increased NbC content to ~92 wt% after 8 h, demonstrating the effectiveness of repeated cold welding and fracturing in promoting carbon dissolution into Nb and subsequent carbide nucleation. The 1:2 mixture exhibited significantly slower carbide formation, most likely due to excess free carbon, hindering solid-state diffusion due to increased lubrication capabilities of the system. This significantly reduced the efficiency of carbon incorporation into the niobium lattice, prolonging the overall MA duration and specific phase yield gains. Considering these results, the 1:1 stoichiometry provides favorable conditions for NbC formation in dry milling.

Microstructural evolution and iron contamination

While dry milling has a higher NbC synthesis rate, XRF measurements reveal the progressive contamination with iron (originating from the stainless steel AISI 420 milling vessel) that occurs with prolonged high-energy milling, as shown in Table 2. After 4 h, the dry-milled 1:1 powder reveals homogeneous distributions of Nb and C, along with a few distinct Fe-enriched regions, as shown in Fig. 11. The prepared powders also showed the presence of a few Si- and O-rich particles, whose origin can be attributed to the milling jar cleaning process, which involves the use of SiC.

Unfortunately, this contamination cannot be avoided even when employing multistep cleaning processes that combine ultrasonic cleaning with the pre-milling of the powder mixture, which is then disposed of to minimize this contamination to a bare minimum. This is consistent with the solubility of Fe in Nb at room temperature, indicating that the progressive abrasion of the steel milling media is due to the nature of MA non-equilibrium processes, which typically significantly increase the mutual solubility of elements. XRF analysis (Table 2) provided a detailed quantification of the Fe contamination in NbC powders. In the PCA-free 1:1 (Nb:C) mixture, Fe increased from 8.67 at.% after 2 h up to 23.21 at.% after 8 h of MA. This behavior corresponds to the XRD results, confirming the formation of Nb-carbides, which steeply increases the wear rate of the milled powders. Although Fe-containing crystalline phases were not detected by XRD, their presence is unambiguously confirmed by EDS and XRF. In fact, the content of Fe is predominantly homogeneously distributed within the interior of the powder particles, suggesting an increased solid solubility of it within the matrix material. On the other hand, a rare presence of a few small Fe shavings was also observed. In direct comparison, the PCA-assisted milling reduced NbC

Fig. 9. XRD spectrum of Nb-C systems measured after 0, 2, 4, 6, and 8 h of mechanical milling: a) Nb:C ratio 1:1 with n-heptane, b) Nb:C ratio 1:2 with n-heptane, c) Nb:C ratio 1:1 without n-heptane, d) Nb:C ratio 1:2 without n-heptane.

Fig. 10. SEM micrographs showing the morphological evolution of the 1:1 Nb–C powder milled with n-heptane for increasing milling durations. (a) 2 h, (b) 4 h, (c) 6 h, and (d) 8 h of MA. Progressive particle refinement, increased fragmentation, and surface roughening indicate enhanced plastic deformation and mechanochemical activation during milling.

Table 2

Relative atomic fractions of Nb and Fe determined by XRF in mechanically alloyed Nb–C powders as a function of PCA use, Nb: C stoichiometry, and milling time. The data highlights the progressive iron contamination of the powder mixture depending on the milling atmosphere and stoichiometry.

PCA (n-heptane)	Nb: C Ratio	Atomic %	Time of MA			
			2 h	4 h	6 h	8 h
With	1:1	Nb	95.45	94.12	93.81	93.58
		Fe	4.55	5.88	6.19	6.42
	1:2	Nb	95.88	94.26	94.01	93.92
		Fe	4.12	5.74	5.99	6.08
Without	1:1	Nb	91.33	85.66	79.6	76.79
		Fe	8.67	14.34	20.4	23.21
	1:2	Nb	85.63	82.72	84.96	82.14
		Fe	14.37	17.25	15.04	17.86

formation, thereby suppressing jar abrasion and, consequently, Fe contamination, as shown in Table 2.

The potential for Fe substitution within the NbC lattice was evaluated based on the thermodynamic framework of the Fe–Nb–C system. While high-energy mechanical alloying can introduce Fe from the milling media, thermodynamic assessments (Equations (1) and (2) [77]) indicate that NbC possesses a significantly higher negative Gibbs free energy of formation compared to iron-based carbides at the sintering temperature of 1000 °C.

Specifically, ΔG_{NbC} is calculated to be approximately -159 kJ/mol, whereas ΔG_{Fe_3C} remains notably higher at approximately -2 kJ/mol. Furthermore, experimental data and CALPHAD modeling suggest that Fe solubility within the NbC phase is strictly limited to approximately 3.57 wt% at 1000 °C [78]. These thermodynamic constraints confirm

Fig. 11. Microstructural and chemical characterization of the 1:1 Nb–C powder milled for 4 h without n-heptane. (a) Optical micrograph showing heterogeneous particle morphology; (b–c) SEM images revealing extensive particle fracturing resulting in the formation of lamellae; (d) SEM micrographs accompanied by (e–h) EDS elemental distribution maps for Nb, Fe, C, and O, confirming Fe contamination. (etched in diluted aqua regia).

that the reinforcement phase is primarily pure NbC, with the iron matrix acting as a metallic solvent rather than a major constituent of the carbide phase [79]. This presumption is further supported by the Fe–Nb–C ternary phase diagram calculated at 1273 K and 48 MPa (Fig. 12), which indicates the preferential stability of Nb-rich carbide phases, particularly non-stoichiometric NbC_x, represented by the carbon-deficient Nb₈C₇ phase. This agrees with the experimental observation that the selected 1:1 Nb:C precursor milled for 4 h without n-heptane contained approximately 19 wt% NbC and a highly reactive Nb(C) fraction that transformed further into NbC during SPS. Although XRF revealed Fe contamination of about 14.34 at.% for this precursor, originating from wear of the stainless-steel milling media, no crystalline Fe₃C was detected in the compact material. The absence of Fe₃C is attributed to the preferential consumption of carbon by Nb and to dilution of Fe within the CoCrFeNiMn matrix. Thus, the thermodynamic prediction supports Nb₈C₇/NbC_x as the dominant carbide phase, while Fe is expected to remain mainly dissolved in the metallic matrix rather than forming a separate carbide phase.

Regarding the balance between carbide formation and Fe contamination, the 1:1 (Nb:C) sample, milled for 4 h without PCA, was selected as the optimal precursor for reinforcing the CoCrFeNiMn HEA. This choice is motivated by the moderate Fe contamination (~14 at.%), which is significantly lower than in long-duration (6–8 h) samples and is therefore closer to the intended NbC composition. More importantly, the powder already contains ~19 wt% NbC alongside highly deformed Nb supersaturated with C. This phase appears to be very reactive, as the major carbide reaction and transformation occur between 4 and 6 h of MA (Table 1). By selecting the 4 h MA powder, introduced here as an

NbC–Nb(C) composite, a favorable environment is provided for completing the in-situ transformation into NbC during the Spark Plasma Sintering (SPS) process. Consequently, the 4 h NbC–Nb(C) powder was used to reinforce the CoCrFeNiMn matrix, hereafter referred to as the NbC–Nb(C) composite.

3.3. Mechanical properties of NbC-reinforced CoCrFeNiMn alloy

3.3.1. XRD and XRF analysis of NbC–Nb(C) reinforced CoCrFeNiMn alloy

The CoCrFeNiMn alloy has been reinforced with NbC–Nb(C) particles at three concentrations: 5, 10, and 15 wt%. The phase composition of both the powder mixture and the SPSed compact has been confirmed by XRD analysis, which is shown in Table 3 and Fig. 13.

XRD results for mixed powder before SPS compaction show that the CoCrFeNiMn alloy is composed of an FCC solid solution, but the CoCrFeNiMn–NbC–Nb(C) composite is not in a complete crystal form, as the normalized XRD results show a higher concentration for the CoCrFeNiMn alloy. The primary reason is that the NbC–Nb(C) composite powder is partially crystalline, while some of the C within the powder mixture might still be present in an amorphous state. However, the XRD results of the mixed powder after SPS compaction show only the presence of FCC solid solution and NbC, while the Nb phase disappears; the concentration rate of the two crystalline components approaches the initial mixing powder fraction. This can be concluded from the SPS compaction of the remaining Nb supersaturated by C, which undergoes an in-situ phase transformation into the NbC phase.

Regarding the presence of n-heptane during milling, it acts primarily as a high-efficiency PCA that dictates the morphological evolution of the

Fig. 12. Fe–Nb–C ternary phase diagram calculated at 1273 K under the applied SPS pressure of 48 MPa (FactSage with FactPS database).

Table 3

Normalized XRD results of mixed NbC–Nb(C) composite and CoCrFeNiMn powder before SPS compacting and after SPS compacting in 3 different NbC–Nb(C) composite concentrations, namely NbC 5,10, and 15 wt% and their XRD patterns.

	Phase	Ref. Code	NbC 5 wt%	NbC 10 wt%	NbC 15 wt%
Mixed powder before SPS	CoCrFeNiMn	04-022-8761	98	97	91
	NbC	01-083-8756	2	2	5
	Nb	04-001-2736	~0	1	4
Composite after SPS	CoCrFeNiMn	04-022-8761	93	91	87
	NbC	01-083-8756	7	9	13
	Nb	04-001-2736	0	0	0

CoCrFeNiMn matrix rather than its long-term chemical phase transformation. According to Lomayeva et al. [80], n-heptane effectively inhibits the severe cold-welding typically observed in dry milling, allowing the metallic particles to reach a nanocrystalline state - potentially as small as 11 nm - within the first hour of treatment. Although n-heptane is a liquid hydrocarbon, the relatively short milling duration in this study likely limits carbon absorption to a thin adsorbed surface layer or early-stage diffusion into near-boundary distorted zones, rather than the formation of secondary carbide phases which literature suggests requires significantly longer milling times (up to 99 h) [80,81]. Furthermore, compared to other PCAs such as ethanol or stearic acid, n-heptane introduces substantially lower levels of carbon pollution, thereby preserving the elemental purity of the Cantor alloy while facilitating the fine dispersion of the NbC reinforcement [81]. Consequently, the n-heptane-assisted milling for 30 min creates a high-surface-area, non-passivated powder that is structurally refined but chemically distinct from the bulk carbon contamination introduced by the primary polypropylene waste carbon source.

To gain insight into the elemental composition, XRF analysis was performed after SPS compaction, as shown in Table 4. The XRF results revealed the presence of matrix-alloy elements, along with an increasing

Table 4

XRF analysis of compacted CoCrFeNiMn alloy composited with NbC via SPS in three different initial NbC powder concentrations.

Element	NbC 5 wt%	NbC 10 wt%	NbC 15 wt%
Cr	16.95 ± 0.1	16.62 ± 0.1	15.03 ± 0.1
Mn	18.03 ± 0.1	17.26 ± 0.1	16.39 ± 0.1
Fe	18.80 ± 0.1	18.38 ± 0.1	17.62 ± 0.1
Co	17.77 ± 0.1	17.30 ± 0.1	15.76 ± 0.1
Ni	21.63 ± 0.2	21.46 ± 0.1	19.99 ± 0.1
Nb	6.17 ± 0.1	8.45 ± 0.1	14.68 ± 0.1

content of Nb, corresponding to the increasing amount of Nb within the composite. Measurement by the XRF technique cannot detect the light elements, which is why the carbon concentration is missing in the table. The elemental and phase analysis confirm once more that the selected NbC–Nb(C) composite powder was a proper choice, combining the multiple effects, starting from time-efficiency, desired phase composition, minimizing the deleterious contamination of the prepared carbides, and prolonging the lifespan of the milling jar due to the in-situ formation of NbC phase during the SPS compacting.

3.3.2. Microstructure of sintered composites

The microstructure of the SPS-consolidated composites was analysed to evaluate the distribution of reinforcing particles and overall densification. The etched samples revealed a fully dense structure with occasional porosity situated at the grain boundaries across all compositions. Considering that porosity is primarily present in the areas of the carbides, this could be caused by the grinding of the samples (e.g., due to carbide particles being torn off the composite matrix), as shown in Fig. 14.

The microstructure consists of an equiaxed FCC solid-solution matrix with clearly defined grain boundaries, and the reinforcing particles are initially thought to be foremostly located at the grain boundaries. However, the carbides were also present within the powder grains, replicating the inner grain boundaries of the existing FCC phases, as further confirmed by etching and, most importantly, by the more detailed SEM analysis.

A detailed SEM analysis illustrates the dispersion of the reinforcing phase, as shown in Fig. 15. Since the images are taken in backscattered

Fig. 13. XRD pattern of HEAs and NbC-Nb(C) mixed powder and after SPS compaction in three concentrations of a) 5, b) 10, and c) 15 wt%.

Fig. 14. Optical micrographs of the SPS-consolidated CoCrFeNiMn composites containing varying NbC fractions: (a) polished surface before etching; (b) microstructure revealed after etching.

electron (BSE) mode, the contrast is primarily dependent on atomic number. The CoCrFeNiMn matrix appears in darker grey tones due to its lower average atomic numbers, and NbC particles appear brighter because Nb has a significantly higher atomic number. Very bright

regions correspond to Nb-rich phases or agglomerated NbC, while darker pores or cracks appear black. In the 15 wt% NbC composite, the carbide particles form a semi-continuous network along the grain boundaries of the matrix. While some agglomeration is visible, the

Fig. 15. SEM micrographs (BSE mode) showing the microstructure of CoCrFeNiMn composites reinforced with: a&e) 5 wt% NbC, b&f) 10 wt% NbC, c&g) 15 wt% NbC, and d&h) pure CoCrFeNiMn without NbC (e-h are etched).

overall distribution suggests that mechanical milling partially distributed the NbC precursors, facilitating their incorporation into the metallic matrix. This intergranular reinforcement architecture is crucial for restricting grain growth, inhibiting dislocation movement during mechanical loading.

The BSE mode SEM micrographs reveal a clear effect of NbC content on the microstructural evolution of the CoCrFeNiMn matrix. At low magnification, the composite containing 15 wt% NbC exhibits a high-volume fraction of bright Nb-rich phases that are frequently interconnected and preferentially located along grain boundaries and triple junctions, indicating particle agglomeration and boundary decoration. Reducing the NbC content to 10 wt% results in a more homogeneous distribution of reinforcement particles, with improved matrix continuity and reduced clustering. In the composite with 5 wt% NbC, the reinforcement particles are sparsely and uniformly dispersed, and the microstructure is dominated by a continuous CoCrFeNiMn matrix with minimal grain boundary coverage by NbC.

High-magnification observations further highlight the role of NbC content on interfacial characteristics and defect formation, as all the composites exhibited gaps at the matrix-NbC interfaces. In the 15 wt% NbC composite, angular NbC particles form particle-rich regions where microcracks and local debonding are evident, suggesting stress concentration and reduced fracture resistance. In contrast, the 10 wt% NbC

composite exhibits well-embedded NbC particles with clean interfaces and limited cracking, indicating more effective load transfer between the matrix and reinforcement. The 5 wt% NbC composite exhibits isolated NbC particles surrounded by a plastically accommodating matrix, which is favorable for fracture toughness but may provide a lower strengthening contribution. Overall, the microstructural features suggest that an intermediate NbC content provides the most balanced reinforcement morphology for enhanced mechanical performance.

To obtain a more reliable assessment of the SPS-consolidated microstructure and to distinguish true microstructural features from preparation artefacts, selected unreinforced CoCrFeNiMn and CoCrFeNiMn + NbC samples were examined by EBSD/EDS after PECS ion polishing Fig. 14. This preparation route substantially reduced surface deformation, topographic relief, carbide pull-out, and etching-related grooves, which are particularly critical when analysing hard carbide-containing composites.

The unreinforced CoCrFeNiMn alloy (Fig. 16a–c) showed a single-phase fcc solid solution microstructure with heterogeneous/random IPF colouring and no dominant crystallographic texture. In the high-resolution $25 \times 25 \mu\text{m}^2$ EBSD map acquired with a step size of $0.03 \mu\text{m}$, 195 grains were detected. The mean grain area was $0.458 \mu\text{m}^2$, corresponding to an equivalent circle diameter (ECD) of approximately $0.76 \mu\text{m}$. The area-weighted mean grain area was $2.613 \mu\text{m}^2$,

Fig. 16. EBSD/EDS analysis of SPS-consolidated CoCrFeNiMn (a–c) and CoCrFeNiMn + 15 wt% NbC (d–f) samples after PECS ion polishing: (a,d) IPF + grain-boundary maps of FCC phase, (b,e) band contrast, and (c,f) EDS elemental maps of the investigated alloys.

corresponding to an area-weighted ECD of approximately 1.82 μm . The boundary network was dominated by 93.4% high-angle grain boundaries, with 6.64% low-angle boundaries.

The CoCrFeNiMn + NbC composite (Fig. 16d–f) exhibited a more heterogeneous microstructure because of the presence of NbC-rich regions. A EBSD map, covering $100 \times 100 \mu\text{m}^2$ with a step size of 0.3 μm , confirmed heterogeneous microstructure because of the presence of NbC-rich regions. In this map, 1317 FCC grains were detected. The mean grain area was 7.903 μm^2 , corresponding to an ECD of approximately 3.17 μm , while the area-weighted mean grain area was 27.608 μm^2 , corresponding to an area-weighted ECD of approximately 5.93 μm . The fraction of low-angle boundaries was only 2.23%, whereas high-angle boundaries accounted for 97.77% of the boundary network. These results show that the composite alloy is characterized by an equiaxed FCC microstructure, a predominantly high-angle boundary network, and no pronounced texture. On the other hand, the areas enriched in Nb corresponding to a presence of NbC, did not provide sufficient Kikuchi bands for indexing.

This indicates that the NbC-rich regions contain fine carbide features. This microstructural morphology is consistent with the monotonic increase in compressive yield strength with increasing NbC addition, as the fine carbide-rich regions and boundary-decorating NbC features can contribute to load transfer, grain-boundary pinning, and constrained plastic flow of the FCC matrix.

The EBSD/EDS observations also provide important insight into the interpretation of dark features observed in SEM images when cross-sections were prepared by a conventional method composed of grinding, polishing, and etching in diluted aqua regia (Fig. 16). In carbide-containing composites, such regions originate from carbide pull-out during grinding and polishing, topographic relief around hard carbide particles, etching grooves, shadowing effects, or EBSD zero-resolution pixels caused by local surface quality rather than by real voids. When prepared by PECS ion polishing (Fig. 15), the appearance of such areas is significantly reduced, as confirmed above. Therefore, the black regions visible in conventionally prepared cross-sections (Fig. 17) should not be considered as porosity. The actual porosity is, in fact, extremely low when ion polishing techniques, that completely mitigate particle pull-outs and suppress grain-boundary etching, are used.

Fig. 17. SEM image of the CoCrFeNiMn + 15 wt% NbC compact composite sample prepared by PECS ion polishing showing significantly lower porosity.

3.3.3. Mechanical properties

The effect of recycled-carbon-derived NbC reinforcement on the mechanical properties of the CoCrFeNiMn high-entropy alloy was assessed through Vickers hardness (HV30) testing and uniaxial compression. The results, summarized in Table 5 and Fig. 18, demonstrate a clear dependence of mechanical performance on the NbC content, which improves the compressive yield strength, while hardness exceed that of the reference alloy only at 15 wt% NbC.

A monotonic strengthening trend was observed across all composite variants. Hardness increased from 248 ± 7 HV30 for the 5 wt% NbC up to 310 ± 9 HV30 for the 15 wt% NbC composite. A similar evolution occurred in compressive yield strength (CYS), which reached 717 ± 36 MPa at a 15 wt% NbC content. These improvements align with typical strengthening mechanisms in particle-reinforced HEAs, including: (a) load transfer from the ductile FCC matrix to stiff NbC particles, (b) Orowan strengthening arising from particle–dislocation interactions, (c) microstructural refinement introduced by high-energy milling and rapid SPS consolidation. As NbC particles were predominantly located at grain boundaries, the Orowan strengthening mechanism is expected to make the smallest contribution among the aforementioned strengthening mechanisms.

All composites exhibited significant compressive plasticity, withstanding strains exceeding 40% without fracturing. This indicates that NbC additions up to 15 wt% do not lead to catastrophic embrittlement under compressive loading, even with the preferential localization of NbC particles at the grain boundaries. While compression testing inherently suppresses crack propagation and may overestimate global ductility compared to tensile loading, the observed behaviour suggests that the discontinuous nature of the reinforcing particles allows the FCC

Table 5

Mechanical properties (Vickers hardness and compressive yield strength) of CoCrFeNiMn composites reinforced with 5, 10, and 15 wt% NbC compared with the unreinforced reference alloy.

Composite	CYS (MPa)	HV 30
5 wt% NbC	530 ± 6	248 ± 7
10 wt% NbC	616 ± 26	270 ± 5
15 wt% NbC	717 ± 36	310 ± 9
CoCrFeNiMn reference alloy	511 ± 22	271 ± 2

Fig. 18. Compressive stress–strain curves of CoCrFeNiMn alloy reinforced with 5, 10, and 15 wt% NbC compared with the unreinforced reference alloy.

matrix to retain substantial flow capacity. This high tolerance for deformation in the presence of relatively coarse carbides suggests a sufficient interfacial integrity under compressive loading and a matrix capable of significant work hardening, although further tensile characterization would be required to fully map the strength-ductility trade-off. This suggests that higher reinforcement levels could potentially be incorporated in future work without inducing brittleness in compression.

Comparing the composites with the unreinforced reference alloy reveals an interesting trend where the hardness initially decreases with the addition of NbC and exceeds that of the reference alloy only when the content of NbC reaches 15 wt%. The underlying reason for this behaviour is primarily attributed to an insufficient volume fraction of NbC at 5 and 10 wt% to provide effective bulk hardening, while the presence of NbC particles disrupts the original cohesion and metallic necking between matrix particles. Furthermore, during mechanical milling, solid-solution distortion may occur due to minor elemental migration into the CoCrFeNiMn lattice, potentially lowering the matrix hardness until a critical reinforcement volume is reached to compensate. Therefore, the volume fraction of the reinforcement plays the dominant role in the composite hardness, with significant strengthening only realized at the 15 wt%. The reference alloy, despite exhibiting a slightly higher hardness of 271 ± 2 HV30, showed a somewhat lower CYS compared to the composite alloys. This suggests that the composites accommodated limited amounts of finely dispersed NbC particles within the FCC grain interiors, with this amount increasing slightly with increasing reinforcing particle content. The EBSD results support this interpretation. The unreinforced CoCrFeNiMn alloy after PECS preparation is characterized by presence of FCC solid solution grains with a predominantly high-angle boundary network and no dominant texture. The NbC-containing composite, in contrast, contains fine/sub-micrometer NbC-rich regions beyond the resolution capabilities of EBSD. Such fine carbide-rich regions can contribute to strengthening

through load transfer, boundary pinning, and constrained plastic deformation of the fcc matrix. At low NbC contents, however, the reinforcement fraction is not sufficient to produce a clear macrohardness increase, and the indentation response remains strongly affected by matrix deformation, local heterogeneity, and possible pull-out/interface artefacts. This explains why the compressive yield strength increases already at 5 wt% NbC, whereas hardness exceeds that of the unreinforced alloy only at the highest investigated reinforcement content of 15 wt% NbC.

This behaviour indicates that the milling process affects the pure alloy and the composite mixtures differently. Hypothetically, milling of the pure alloy is assumed to induce severe work hardening and microstructural refinement, maximizing the strength of the matrix itself. In the composite powders, the hard NbC particles may reduce the effective strain imparted to the ductile matrix (shielding effect), resulting in a lower degree of matrix work hardening. Moreover, it has been demonstrated that the milling process distributes the reinforcing NbC particles within the FCC solid-solution grain interiors only to a limited extent; instead, the particles are preferentially and more homogeneously located along the grain boundaries. As a result, the increase in CYS becomes much less than one would expect when the particles are homogeneously distributed within the grain's interior.

4. Environmental and sustainability screening of secondary carbon production

4.1. Scope and methodological assumptions

A screening-level environmental assessment was performed to contextualize the production of solid secondary carbon obtained during microwave plasma gasification of waste PP. This analysis does not represent a full cradle-to-gate LCA; instead, it evaluates selected process-level indicators relevant to carbon precursor production. The functional

Table 6
Definition of selected operating conditions (OC 1–OC 5).

Parameter	OC 1	OC 2	OC 3	OC 4	OC 5
PP Feed Rate (kg/h)	6.0 ± 0.3	10.0 ± 0.3	16 ± 0.3	18 ± 0.3	18 ± 0.3
Plasma Power Input (kW)	20 ± <1	40 ± <1	40 ± <1	40 ± <1	40 ± <1
CO ₂ Input (slm)	0	0	0	0	46 ± 5

Table 7
Electricity generation carbon intensities used for scenario analysis.

Country	Electricity generation carbon intensity (gCO ₂ eq./kWh)
Czech Republic (EEA)	332 ± 33
Sweden (EEA)	7 ± 1
Poland (EEA)	554 ± 55
EU27 avg. (EEA)	187 ± 19
EU27 avg. (EMBER)	213 ± 21
Global avg. (EMBER)	473 ± 47

unit is defined as 1 kg of recovered solid carbon, with complementary values also reported per 1 kg of processed PP feedstock. The assessment is limited to the plasma processing step. Downstream NbC synthesis and consolidation were excluded, as they are not dependent on the origin of the carbon precursor. For screening purposes, five representative experimental operating conditions (OC 1–OC 5) were selected from previous work [61], covering variations in feed rate, plasma power, and one input CO₂-assisted case, which is shown in Table 6.

Electricity consumption was derived from measured plasma torch power and normalized to both PP processed and recovered carbon. The resulting comparative GWP (Global Warming Potential) values were calculated using electricity-generation carbon intensities for selected countries and averages (Czech Republic, Sweden, Poland, EU27, global). These scenarios are included illustratively, to demonstrate how the environmental performance would vary depending on the geographical electricity mix, rather than to represent fixed deployment locations. Electricity generation carbon intensity is shown in Table 7.

Waste PP feedstock was treated as a zero-burden input. Infrastructure and capital goods were not explicitly inventoried; instead, their contribution was approximated using a +15 ± 5% correction applied to electricity-based GWP results. This is consistent with literature values reporting 1–18% contributions of capital goods to GWP [82], around ~12% in gasification systems [83], and ~2–3% in large-scale incineration plants [84].

In OC 5, CO₂ was used as a technical process gas (46 slm ≈ 5.5 kg h⁻¹). Its contribution to GWP was neglected due to ambiguity in its treatment, as it may represent both an upstream emission (supply and compression) and a potential carbon utilization pathway.

4.2. Process metrics and environmental performance

The results of key process metrics are summarized in Table 8. The energy intensity of PP treatment ranged from 2.22 to 4.00 kWh kg⁻¹ of PP processed, while the carbon-normalized energy demand ranged from 5.4 to 20.8 kWh kg⁻¹ C. The most favorable condition (OC 4) combined

Table 8
Process performance and energy intensity of recovered carbon.

Parameter	OC 1	OC 2	OC 3	OC 4	OC 5
En. Intensity of PP Treatment (kWh/kg)	3.33 ± 0.14	4.00 ± 0.11	2.50 ± 0.05	2.22 ± 0.04	2.22 ± 0.04
Solid C Production (kg/h)	1.0 ± 0.2	3.2 ± 0.3	6.2 ± 1.6	7.5 ± 0.6	6.5 ± 0.2
En. Intensity of Solid C Production (kWh/kg)	20.8 ± 3.5	12.6 ± 1.3	6.5 ± 1.6	5.4 ± 0.5	6.2 ± 0.2
Solid C/Input PP Feed Rate fraction (%)	16 ± 3	32 ± 3	39 ± 10	41 ± 4	36 ± 1
Solid C/C in Input PP Feed Rate fraction (%)	19 ± 3	37 ± 4	45 ± 12	48 ± 4	42 ± 1
Chem. En. (C)/Chem. En. (SG + C) (%)	59 ± 11	71 ± 9	42 ± 12	45 ± 4	37 ± 1

high carbon production (~7.5 kg h⁻¹) with the lowest energy intensity (~5.4 kWh kg⁻¹ C). The recovered solid carbon corresponds to 16–41 wt % of PP feed and 19–48 wt % of the carbon contained in PP. This should be interpreted as recovery of a secondary product, since the process is primarily designed for syngas generation.

In this context, the observed carbon yields are consistent with thermochemical conversion trends. Conventional pyrolysis of plastics (like PP) typically produces mainly liquid hydrocarbons, with solid char yields usually limited to units to low tens of percent, depending on conditions [85–87]. Higher char yields have been observed and reported under specific catalytic conditions, particularly with zeolites such as HZSM-5, LHZSM-5 or NH₄ZSM-5 [85,87]. The plasma process therefore operates in a regime where carbon formation competes with gas-phase conversion at elevated temperatures.

From an energy perspective, the process achieves values comparable to or lower than conventional graphite production, which typically requires 13–31 kWh kg⁻¹ [88–90]. This is particularly evident for optimized and favorable operating conditions (like in cases OC 3–OC 5).

The calculated GWP values (Fig. 19) show a strong dependence on electricity supply. The results demonstrate a clear trend that low-carbon electricity systems (e.g., Sweden) reduce impacts by more than an order of magnitude. Also, high-carbon systems (e.g., Poland) significantly increase the footprint.

Overall, the environmental performance is dominated by electricity consumption, confirming that the process footprint is primarily determined by the energy source rather than by the reactor itself.

Compared with conventional graphite (~5.3–13.8 kg CO₂-eq kg⁻¹ [88–90]), the present route is highly scenario-dependent. Under low-carbon electricity, all operating conditions fall well below this range; under carbon-intensive electricity, only optimized conditions remain competitive.

It should be emphasized that this process is not a dedicated carbon-production pathway. If carbon were the primary objective, other primary sources like methane would be more suitable for pyrolysis, with reported conversion efficiencies to secondary raw products (in this case H₂ + C) of over 90% [91,92]. In contrast, the present process prioritizes waste treatment and syngas production, with carbon recovered as a secondary product.

This positions the route closer to carbon recycling or materials upcycling than to conventional graphite production, which relies on virgin fossil or mineral resources. This interpretation is consistent with recent studies showing improved environmental performance for recycled graphite relative to natural and synthetic routes [93].

4.3. Limitations and relevance of the screening

This assessment represents a screening-level analysis, not a full LCA. A complete cradle-to-gate evaluation would require detailed inventories for infrastructure, equipment manufacturing, maintenance, transport, and auxiliary systems, which are not available for the present laboratory-scale setup.

Additional limitations include the use of literature-based graphite benchmarks with varying system boundaries, and the fact that not all recovered carbon may be directly suitable for NbC synthesis without further processing.

Fig. 19. Carbon intensity of secondary carbon production under different electricity mixes.

Despite these limitations, the results provide a clear first-order insight:

- The process is energy-driven, with electricity mix as the dominant factor.
- The recovered carbon is a secondary product, not the primary process objective, and can be therefore considered as a process waste that needs to be further treated.
- The main environmental benefit lies in waste valorisation and partial substitution of virgin carbon feedstocks, rather than guaranteed GWP reduction in all scenarios.

5. Conclusions

This study successfully demonstrated a strategy for valorising waste polypropylene-derived carbon into high-performance niobium carbide (NbC) reinforcement for high-entropy alloys (HEAs). By investigating the NbC synthesis, microstructural evolution, and final composite performance, the following conclusions are drawn:

Synthesis Optimization: The synthesis of NbC from waste carbon is highly sensitive to processing conditions. Dry mechanical alloying of a 1:1, Nb: C stoichiometric mixture was identified as the optimal route, yielding ~19 wt% NbC after 4 h with a favorable "activated" microstructure (carbon-supersaturated niobium) suitable for further in-situ transformation during the subsequent sintering. Selecting the NbC–Nb (C) composite material at this stage (a) saves energy and time from a techno-economic perspective and (b) minimizes Fe contamination during mechanical alloying, which would otherwise negatively affect the properties of the prepared carbide and shorten the milling-jar lifespan.

Conversely, the use of n-heptane as a process control agent proved counterproductive, inducing pyrophoric behavior and severe oxidation, rendering wet milling unsuitable for this specific material combination and carbide synthesis approach.

Composite Microstructure: Spark Plasma Sintering (SPS) at 1000 °C successfully consolidated the composite powders into dense, compact structures. Microstructural analysis confirmed that the NbC particles were effectively dispersed within the CoCrFeNiMn matrix, primarily occupying grain boundary regions, which restricted grain growth and reinforced the structure.

Mechanical Strengthening: The addition of NbC to the CoCrFeNiMn alloy increased the CYS of the composite, surpassing that of the non-reinforced reference alloy, and continued to rise with increasing NbC content, reaching the highest CYS of 717 ± 36 MPa for the 15 wt% of NbC while retaining excellent compressive plasticity (>40%). On the other hand, the hardness of the reference alloy (271 ± 2 HV30) exceeded that of the 5 wt% NbC composite (248 ± 7 HV30), due to the preferential accumulation of hard NbC particles at the FCC solid-solution grain boundaries, and was comparable to the composite containing 10 wt% NbC. This discrepancy can be attributed to the nature of the matrix–NbC interfaces, which contain gaps that allow the material to undergo localized plastic deformation during indentation, thereby reducing the overall hardness of the reinforced alloys at certain NbC contents.

In summary, this work validates that carbon recovered from plastic waste can be effectively upcycled into high-value ceramic reinforcement, transforming a disposal liability into a strategic resource. This approach may not only provide a high-performance material solution for demanding engineering applications but also pave the way for further research, such as highlighting the need to optimize the intermixing of reinforcing particles, while actively supporting circular economy principles by closing the material loop and reducing the environmental footprint of modern alloy manufacturing.

Data statement

According to Open Science principles, data can be found at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17989162>.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the manuscript preparation process

During the preparation of this work, the authors used ChatGPT, Gemini, and Copilot in order to enhance readability and language quality. After using these tools/services, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper. Data availability.

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